

ASSESSING THE INFLUENCE OF PERCEIVED LEARNING ENVIRONMENT ON MOTIVATION AMONG PHYSICAL EDUCATION MAJOR STUDENTS

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Assessing the Influence of Perceived Learning Environment on Motivation Among Physical Education Major Students

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine which domain of perceived learning environment best predicts the motivation of physical education major students. The study utilized a quantitative method of research using correlational technique. A total of 221 students from three universities in Davao City were identified through stratified random sampling. Mean, Pearson r , and regression analysis were used as statistical tools of the study. Results revealed a very high level of perceived learning environment among physical education major students. In addition, students also demonstrated a high level of motivation. Moreover, results showed a significant, positive, but weak relationship between perceived learning environment and motivation of students, with effort/improvement and intra-class rivalry identified as the strongest predictors of student motivation. These findings provide valuable insights into the complex interplay between the learning environment and student motivation within the context of physical education, offering implications for educators and policymakers aiming to optimize learning experiences and outcomes for PE major students.

Keywords: *learning environment, motivation, physical education students, predictor*

Introduction

The dynamic interplay between the learning environment and student motivation has long been recognized as a crucial determinant of academic success and achievement (Kurniawan et al., 2023; Abdullah et al., 2023; Havidz & Mujakiah, 2023; Susiani et al., 2022). Within the realm of higher education, understanding this intricate relationship holds particular significance, especially in specialized fields such as physical education. As educators and institutions strive to cultivate an environment conducive to learning and growth, exploring the influence of perceived learning environment on student motivation becomes imperative. Physical education programs play a pivotal role in shaping the knowledge, skills, and attitudes of future educators and practitioners in the field. Beyond the traditional classroom setting, these programs often incorporate experiential learning, practical training, and collaborative activities to enrich students' educational experiences (Calubayan & Ofrin, 2023; Couto et al., 2023). However, the extent to which the perceived learning environment within physical education settings impacts student motivation remains an area warranting further investigation.

Lack of motivation presents a formidable challenge for both educators and students within the classroom, exerting a significant impact on the overall learning environment and educational outcomes (Patrick, 2023). This issue becomes particularly pronounced in the context of physical education, where the effectiveness of classes is intricately tied to the perceived learning environment and the level of student motivation. As highlighted by several studies, a concerning trend emerges as a number of students disengage from their education, with motivational deficiencies cited as a primary contributing factor (Oliveira & Lathrop, 2022; Alamdari & Sullivan, 2016; Ford, 2014). The persistent detachment of a substantial portion of students underscores the urgency of addressing motivational challenges within educational settings. Students who exhibit signs of boredom or disinterest, and consequently invest less effort into their academic tasks, are less likely to derive benefit from advancements in educational standards, curriculum development, and instructional methodologies (Guo & Chang, 2023; Amiri et al., 2022; Volkova, 2022). This pervasive lack of motivation not only compromises individual academic achievement but also poses a broader societal concern, as it undermines efforts to foster a culture of lifelong learning and intellectual growth.

Extensive research has underscored the crucial role of the perceived learning environment in shaping academic achievement and various other relevant student outcomes (Soltani et al., 2022; Cahyati et al., 2022; Tunçsiper & Mutlu, 2020; Kohoulat et al., 2017). This body of evidence illustrates the profound impact that the learning environment exerts on students' educational experiences and overall success. Moreover, according to Key (2023) and Давлетова and Тафеева (2022), an optimal learning environment is one that caters to the diverse needs of students, providing clean and hygienic premises while minimizing potential risks for injuries during both indoor and outdoor activities. This perspective underscores the multifaceted nature of the learning environment, encompassing physical, social, and emotional dimensions that collectively influence students' learning outcomes. The way teachers and students perceive the environment where activities of teaching and learning take place, tell whether the environment is adequate or inadequate for the expected learning outcome.

With the recent studies and findings on the two variables, this study aims to address this gap by assessing the influence of perceived learning environment on motivation among physical education major students. Limited studies have surfaced in the literature showing the relationship of learning environment and motivation among physical education students and in the locality of Davao City, Philippines. By examining the perceptions of physical education students regarding various aspects of their learning environment and correlating these with their motivation levels, valuable insights can be gained into the factors that contribute to or hinder student

engagement and enthusiasm within this academic domain. Furthermore, the results of this study would prove beneficial for universities offering physical education major courses, enabling them to establish stronger connections with stakeholders such as school administrators, teachers, parents, and students. Additionally, the findings would contribute to the cultivation of motivated students who exhibit higher levels of academic achievement and possess sustainable skills.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine which domain of perceived learning environment best influences motivation of students. Specifically, it was directed to give answers to the following questions:

1. What is the level of perceived learning environment of PE majors in terms of:
 - 1.1 effort or improvement;
 - 1.2 important role;
 - 1.3 cooperative learning;
 - 1.4 punishment for mistakes;
 - 1.5 unequal recognition; and
 - 1.6 intra- class rivalry?
2. What is the level of motivation of PE majors in terms of:
 - 2.1. intrinsic motivation;
 - 2.2. extrinsic motivation; and
 - 2.3. amotivation?
3. Is there a significant relationship between perceived learning environment and motivation of PE majors?
4. Which domain of perceived learning environment best influences motivation of PE majors?

Literature Review

Perceived Learning Environment

Learning environment exemplifies not just like the physical space but also the entire learning area which consists of instructional processes, teacher-student partnership, student-student relationships, and their attitudes. Also, it is described in terms of tangible characteristics like school buildings, instructional materials, and observed interactions among students and teachers in the outside environment. Alternatively, learning environments is described as teachers' or students' personal view of their learning setting (Hayat et al., 2016). In other word, learning environment described the social, psychological, or psychosocial environment where learning and teaching happens (Cleveland & Fisher, 2014). In addition, Youssef et al. (2013) defined the learning environment as the relevant manifestation and conceptualization of curriculum including educational and organizational that grip everything that is taking place in the medical arena.

Effort/Improvement. A significant aspect of the perceived learning environment in physical education, encompasses students' commitment to giving their best to achieve their goals. According to the National Association for Sport and Physical Education (2009), physical education students are expected to engage in physical activity for a substantial portion of each lesson. While teachers may assess the effort exerted by students, there is no mandatory requirement to evaluate this level of activity. The inclusion of effort assessment in grading performance remains a subject of debate. Although a considerable portion of lesson time is dedicated to physical activity, the assessment of participation or effort contributes to the grading criteria in physical education (Lund & Tannehill, 2010). Effort serves as a fundamental component of educational assessment, influencing decision-making processes. However, it is notable that effort is not explicitly mandated by state curriculums, which primarily focus on quantifiable outcomes such as knowledge acquisition, psychomotor development, and physical health maintenance (Baghurst, 2014).

Important Role. It is essential to consider students' active involvement and responsibility in the learning process. Important role pertains to students' function within the learning environment and their active participation in shaping their educational experiences. As emphasized by Price-Mitchell (2015), students demonstrate their important role when they take ownership of their learning success and actively engage in actions that align with their educational aspirations. Moreover, while teachers play a crucial role in developing classroom management plans to facilitate effective learning environments (Ministry of Education, Guyana, 2013), students also bear responsibility in contributing to the implementation of a quality learning environment. This begins with adhering to individual rules and expectations, demonstrating self-respect, and meeting behavioral and academic expectations. Price-Mitchell (2015) highlights that students who take ownership of their actions exhibit behaviors such as integrity, honesty, punctuality, and respectful communication with peers and teachers. Additionally, they engage in activities outside of class, respect social environments and policies, seek help when needed, value diverse perspectives, and actively pursue their educational goals. Thus, students' recognition and fulfillment of their important role contribute significantly to the overall learning environment and academic success.

Cooperative Learning. It is crucial to consider the collaborative aspects of the learning environment. Cooperative Learning involves student-student and student-teacher interaction aimed at accomplishing tasks collaboratively. As outlined by Castle Jr. (2018), it is a strategy that fosters interdependence among small groups to achieve collective recognition. Furthermore, Wadawi (2013) distinguishes

cooperative learning from group learning techniques by highlighting its rigorous structures, including systematic management, role assignments, supervision, and performance evaluation. The benefits of cooperative learning are multifaceted, catering to students across diverse academic skill levels (Millis, 2009). The essence of cooperative learning lies in its components such as positive interdependence, face-to-face interaction, individual accountability, social skills development, and group processing (Habi, 2010). This approach to learning has garnered significant attention in educational research, spanning various contexts including regular and special education, as well as social and clinical settings (Ferraro, 2015). As Denton (2014) notes, cooperative learning fosters a collaborative environment where students in small groups actively engage in helping each other learn, emphasizing mutual support and collective achievement. Thus, cooperative learning emerges as a vital component of education, promoting collaboration, social interaction, and academic success among students.

Punishment for Mistakes. This encompasses the consequences meted out by teachers when students err. This disciplinary approach, also prevalent among parents, aims to regulate student behavior (Lawrent, 2012). Psychologists characterize punishment as a deterrent, involving the reduction of undesirable behavior through means such as physical discomfort, loss of privileges, or warnings. While punishment aims to instill fear and deterrence, its efficacy and ethical implications have come under scrutiny. The United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child deems corporal punishment ineffective and harmful, advocating for its elimination in schools and homes (Murphy & Virgins, 2010). Article 28(2) of the Convention emphasizes that school discipline should uphold the dignity of the child, denouncing severe punishment for its potential to inflict pain, humiliation, and long-term psychological harm. Despite international efforts to abolish corporal punishment, it persists in some regions where students endure physical abuse and its detrimental effects on mental health and academic performance (URT, 2006).

Moreover, studies highlight the adverse consequences of punitive disciplinary measures on students' cognitive and behavioral development. Talwar et al. (2011) found that exposure to corporal punishment correlates with poorer academic performance and deficits in verbal intelligence and executive functioning. Additionally, Rahimi and Karkami (2015) investigated the impact of coercive discipline in Australia, revealing its inhibitory effect on student engagement and academic achievement. These findings underscore the importance of adopting alternative disciplinary approaches that prioritize positive reinforcement, conflict resolution, and restorative justice to foster a safe and supportive learning environment conducive to student well-being and academic success.

Unequal Recognition. This is a pervasive issue in classrooms, denotes the biased treatment of students by teachers. This form of favoritism, often subtle, corrodes morale and undermines the integrity of classroom dynamics (Linsin, 2020). Research suggests that teachers may exhibit favoritism towards certain students, leading to unequal treatment within the classroom (Aydogan, 2008). This unequal recognition not only erodes the principles of fairness and equality but also undermines the educational objectives of the classroom (Nadler & Schulman, 2006). Aristotle's ethical premise that "equals should be treated equally and unequals unequally" underscores the importance of fairness in educational settings. Unequal recognition disrupts this principle by bestowing undeserved benefits upon some students while depriving others (Mechtenberg, 2006). Consequently, addressing unequal recognition is imperative for promoting fairness, fostering a supportive learning environment, and upholding the ethical principles of education.

Intra-Class Rivalry. The phenomenon of competition within the classroom environment encompasses various dynamics that influence student behavior and well-being. Competition often arises as students vie for the approval of their teachers, seeking validation that transcends mere academic achievement (Heinrich, 2014). This quest for approval can manifest in various forms, including competition for grades and rewards among peers. Such rivalry intensifies when individuals or groups perceive a scarcity of desired outcomes, leading to heightened competition for attainment (Shindler, 2009). Unfortunately, the prevalence of competition in educational settings has been associated with concerning trends in mental health, particularly in the United States, where an increase in psychopathologies correlates with heightened competitive behaviors (Gilbert et al., 2009). The World Health Organization has identified depression as a significant mental health issue, exacerbated by factors such as self-harm and social comparisons fueled by competitive environments. Gilbert et al. (2009) further suggest that individuals experiencing depression may attribute their perceived failures in competition to personal shortcomings, exacerbating feelings of inadequacy and low self-esteem.

In the context of the school environment, the pervasiveness of competition can have detrimental effects on students' mental well-being and self-esteem. It is crucial for educators to create an environment that fosters recognition of students' efforts and accomplishments, promotes supportive peer relationships, and offers avenues for positive reinforcement beyond the confines of competition. By prioritizing holistic student development and creating a culture of collaboration and support, educators can mitigate the negative impacts of competition on students' mental health and foster a more inclusive and nurturing learning environment.

Motivation

Motivation plays a pivotal role in shaping students' engagement and participation in physical education activities (Cox et al., 2008; Shen et al., 2010). Research indicates that motivated students demonstrate higher levels of physical activity both during class sessions (How et al., 2013; Lonsdale et al., 2013; Lonsdale et al., 2009) and in pursuit of goals outside the classroom (Standage et al., 2003). Furthermore, motivated students are more likely to experience positive changes in their overall physical education experiences (Zhang, 2009) and exhibit a sustained motive for future participation (Shen et al., 2012). Given these findings, it stands to reason that physical education programs have a more profound and positive impact on motivated students (Haerens et al., 2010).

Intrinsic motivation. Intrinsic motivation embodies the natural inclination towards accepting and engaging with tasks or activities. It encompasses the innate desire to tackle challenges, utilize skills, and pursue personal goals (Saeedeh et al., 2016). Individuals who are intrinsically motivated typically experience a sense of enjoyment, interest, and feelings of competence and autonomy when engaging in activities (Gutierrez et al., 2010). Moreover, they willingly participate in activities for the inherent enjoyment they provide, rather than solely for external rewards or compliance with imposed constraints (Taylor et al., 2014). Intrinsic motivation represents an internal drive to engage with tasks or pursuits (Hilden & Jones, 2011), wherein individuals derive satisfaction and fulfillment from the activity itself rather than external incentives. Consequently, intrinsically motivated individuals often exhibit self-regulated behavior, actively managing their engagement with tasks based on personal preferences and intrinsic satisfaction (Anhuis, 2013). Thus, the inherent fulfillment derived from task engagement serves as the primary reward for intrinsically motivated individuals, obviating the need for external reinforcement.

Extrinsic Motivation. Extrinsic motivation is characterized by the external factors that drive individuals to engage in specific tasks or activities. It revolves around the pursuit of outcomes or rewards external to the task itself, motivating individuals to work based on the perceived value of the associated rewards (Kusurkar et al., 2011). Within the framework of achievement goal theory, motivation is influenced by the types of goals individuals set for themselves in their tasks or routines (Spittle, 2014; Isoard-Gautheur et al., 2013). Students who exhibit extrinsic motivation often prioritize external rewards and recognition over the inherent value of the task itself, such as seeking grades or praise rather than understanding the content (Houghton, 2015). Their participation in activities may be driven by the desire to achieve better scores, gain approval from teachers, or show respect to peers (Froiland, 2011). However, this external focus may lead to a reduced engagement in classroom activities, as the motivation stems primarily from external rewards rather than intrinsic interest. Moreover, an overemphasis on extrinsic motivation can diminish intrinsic attention and satisfaction for learning, ultimately undermining the quality of task execution and the perceived motivation for engaging in the activity (Crow & Small, 2011). Thus, while extrinsic motivation may initially drive performance, its exclusive focus can lead to negative consequences, hindering genuine engagement and fulfillment in learning tasks.

Amotivation. Amotivation represents a state where individuals lack the drive to make independent decisions and engage in activities. It becomes evident when individuals exhibit passive or indifferent behaviors towards tasks or activities, often resulting in decreased participation or effort (Mazyari et al., 2012). This lack of motivation stems from feelings of incompetence and a perceived lack of control, which can ultimately lead to disengagement and even dropout from educational settings (Jackson-Kersey & Spray, 2015). Individuals experiencing amotivation typically lack self-determination and fail to see the value or relevance of the activity, resulting in poor performance and a lack of effort towards achieving desired outcomes (Deci & Ryan, 2008). Moreover, amotivation can be exacerbated by external factors such as unsupportive learning environments or teaching styles. According to Jackson-Kersey and Spray (2015), amotivation reflects a psychological state where individuals fail to recognize the relationship between their actions and the consequences thereof, leading to a complete absence of motivation. Amotivated individuals may perceive lessons as insignificant, express dissatisfaction with teaching methods, and exhibit behaviors such as poor attendance and memory deficits (Ntoumanis et al., 2004).

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized the descriptive-correlational research design. Creswell (2012) noted that this design aims to measure the degree of association between more than two variables or sets of scores. Similarly, correlation study determines the magnitude and direction of the relationship (Asaad, 2010). In the context of the present study, the design is used to establish the relationship between perceived learning environment and motivation of the physical education major students.

Participants

The study utilized stratified random sampling in selecting the respondents of the study. The study was participated by 221 physical education major students from selected higher educational institutions (HEIs) in Davao City, Philippines. Table 1 shows the number of respondents taken from the different HEIs.

Table 1. Number of respondents per HEI

<i>Strata</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
HEI A	159	69	13.58%
HEI B	189	82	16.14%
HEI C	160	70	13.78%
Total	508	221	43.50%

Instruments

This study adapted two questionnaires from Johnson et al. (2017) and Sulz et al. (2016) which cover perceived learning environment and student motivation, respectively. These questionnaires were subjected to content validation by a pool of experts prior to its distribution to the identified respondents. The validation score is 3.71 which mean good. This indicated that the questionnaire measures

the goal or objective of the study. After passing validation, the questionnaire was pilot tested. This was administered to students not covered in the study. The main purpose is to check the consistency of students' responses based on the items indicated in the questionnaire.

Procedure

A written communication was submitted to the university president requesting permission to conduct study. Once the request was approved, the researchers presented the approved letter to the dean/administrator of the teacher education department for the endorsement to gather data from the physical education major students. Once endorsed, the researchers proceeded with the identification of the study participants. The participants were asked to sign an informed consent and was oriented on the scope and objectives of the study. After the participants have given consent, the questionnaires on perceived learning environment and motivation were administered. Data was organized and tabulated for data analysis. Mean, standard deviation, Pearson r , and regression analysis was used to analyze the data.

Ethical Considerations

Respondents were handed out informed consent and they were oriented on the processes and purpose of the study. No respondent was forced to participate if it is against their will. Moreover, no sanctions were given for those who chose not to participate. Also, anonymity and confidentiality of the respondents and data were considered. Every effort was made to maintain anonymity in any written work resulting from this study.

Results and Discussion

Level of Perceived Learning Environment

Table 2 provides an overview of the perceived learning environment among physical education major students, offering insight into various indicators and their corresponding mean scores, standard deviations, and descriptive levels.

Table 2. *Level of Perceived Learning Environment of PE majors*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
Effort/Improvement	4.54	.43	Very High
Cooperative Learning	4.43	.89	Very High
Important Role	4.40	.34	Very High
Intra- Class Rivalry	3.59	1.01	High
Unequal Recognition	3.30	1.09	Moderate
Punishment for Mistakes	3.21	1.09	Moderate
Overall	3.51	.56	High

As seen in table 2, effort/improvement, cooperative learning, and important role emerged as key facets of the learning environment, receiving mean scores of 4.54, 4.43, and 4.40 respectively, indicating a very high level of perceived significance in these areas. Students view their participation in learning activities as integral, demonstrating a strong commitment to effort, cooperation, and recognizing the importance of their roles within the educational setting. These indicators exhibit low standard deviations, suggesting a high level of consensus among students regarding their perceptions. The result supports the idea that positive learning environment is needed for the improvement of generic skills and foster creativity among students (Virtanen et al., 2022). Moreover, an interactive and cooperative learning environment were reported by several studies to enhance the acquisition of generic skills and creativity (Virtanen & Tynjälä, 2019; Anthony & Garner, 2016).

Intra-class rivalry, although present to some extent with a mean score of 3.59, is categorized as high, implying that while there may be some competition within the class, it does not significantly detract from the overall perceived learning environment. According to Li et al. (2022), class competition positively predicted academic achievement by promoting learning engagement. Moreover, a certain degree of classroom competition and students' attitude to competition are influential toward their academic performance (Wongvorachan, 2023). These results highlight the importance of healthy learning environment by maintaining a healthy competition among students.

However, unequal recognition and punishment for mistakes are perceived at a moderate level, receiving mean scores of 3.30 and 3.21 respectively, along with relatively higher standard deviations. This suggests that students perceive some disparities in recognition and punishment practices within the learning environment, which may impact their overall educational experiences. This is congruent to the findings of Quansah et al. (2022) that negative or unsafe learning environments is positively correlated and is shown to increase the anxiety levels of students. They continued by suggesting that academic departments should offer counselling sessions and interventions such as positive self-talk, mental rehearsal and cognitive restructuring to students encountering this problem.

Level of Motivation of Students

Table 3 offers valuable insights into the level of motivation among physical education (PE) major students, presenting mean scores,

standard deviations (SD), and descriptive levels for different indicators.

Table 3. *Level of Motivation of PE majors*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
Extrinsic Motivation	4.42	.66	Very High
Intrinsic Motivation	4.36	.64	Very High
Amotivation	4.19	.73	High
Overall	4.33	.52	Very High

Based on table 3, extrinsic motivation and intrinsic motivation emerge as prominent aspects of motivation among PE majors, with mean scores of 4.42 and 4.36 respectively, both categorized as very high. These findings indicate a strong inclination among students towards both external rewards and internal satisfaction derived from their engagement in physical education activities. The relatively low standard deviations accompanying these indicators suggest a high level of consistency in students' levels of extrinsic and intrinsic motivation. Amotivation, with a mean score of 4.19 as seen in table 3, is categorized as high. This suggests that while some students may exhibit a lack of motivation, it is not as prevalent or pronounced.

The findings of this study align closely with previous research in the field, as demonstrated by Penus (2023), who observed a high level of motivation among student athletes in physical education. This suggests that student athletes exhibit both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation to a significant extent, contributing to their competence and proficiency in their respective fields. Furthermore, Heredia-León et al. (2023) highlighted the significance of motivational profiles in influencing various outcomes, noting that students classified in high-quality motivational profiles exhibited greater autonomy support, physical activity intention, and enjoyment, while experiencing lower levels of boredom. These findings underscore the importance of considering the quality and quantity of motivation in understanding students' experiences and behaviors within physical education settings. Additionally, Kondratenko et al. (2021) identified multiple factors influencing the motivation levels of physical education major students, including health, aesthetic, professional-oriented, administrative-obligatory, and status-related factors. These findings highlight the multifaceted nature of motivation and the diverse range of influences that shape students' motivational experiences within the context of physical education.

Relationship between Perceived Learning Environment and Motivation of PE majors

Table 4 illustrates the relationship between perceived learning environment factors and the motivation levels of physical education (PE) major students. Each cell in the table represents the correlation coefficient (r) between a specific perceived learning environment indicator and different dimensions of motivation, including intrinsic, extrinsic, and amotivation, as well as the overall motivation score.

Table 4. *Relationship between Perceived Learning Environment and Motivation of PE majors*

<i>Perceived Learning Environment</i>	<i>Motivation</i>			
	<i>Intrinsic</i>	<i>Extrinsic</i>	<i>Amotivation</i>	<i>Overall</i>
Effort/Improvement	.202**	.250**	.205**	.286**
Important Role	.268**	.189**	.088	.231**
Cooperative Learning	.216**	.130	.165*	.220**
Punishment for Mistakes	.036	.014	.112	.070
Unequal Recognition	.088	-.018	.024	.040
Intra-class Rivalry	.218**	-.003	.109	.140*
Overall	.236**	.86	.170*	.212**

Note: * indicates $p < .05$; ** indicates $p < .01$.

Several noteworthy patterns emerge from the analysis as reflected in table 4. Effort/improvement demonstrates significant positive correlations with all dimensions of motivation, with correlation coefficients ranging from .202 to .286, all of which are statistically significant at $p < .01$. This suggests that students who perceive a supportive environment conducive to effort and improvement tend to exhibit higher levels of motivation across the board. Similarly, the perceived importance of students' roles in the learning environment shows positive correlations with intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, with correlation coefficients ranging from .189 to .268, all statistically significant at $p < .01$. This indicates that students who feel valued and integral to the learning process are more likely to be motivated, both intrinsically and extrinsically.

Cooperative learning also displays significant positive correlations with intrinsic and overall motivation, highlighting the importance of collaborative activities in fostering student engagement and enthusiasm for learning. However, the correlation with extrinsic motivation is relatively weaker and not statistically significant. Conversely, punishment for mistakes, unequal recognition, and intra-class rivalry demonstrate either weak or nonsignificant correlations with motivation dimensions, indicating that these aspects of the perceived learning environment may have limited influence on students' motivational levels.

The findings of this study resonate with previous research, as highlighted by Leo et al. (2020), who discovered a positive relationship between a perceived need-supportive learning environment in physical education and students' motivation. This alignment underscores the importance of creating an environment that fosters students' sense of autonomy and competence, ultimately promoting engagement and intentions for physical activity. Similarly, Wu et al. (2021) identified the influence of perceived motivational climate in PE classes on exercise behavior change, particularly through autonomous motivation. This suggests that the motivational climate established

within physical education settings extends beyond the classroom, influencing students' engagement in leisure-time physical activities. Moreover, the study by Niederkofler et al. (2015) sheds light on the impact of perceived climate in PE classes on students' achievement motives. Factors such as teacher care and classmate cooperativeness were found to significantly influence motivation levels among PE majors, further emphasizing the crucial role of the learning environment in shaping students' motivational experiences.

With the findings of this study, it becomes evident that the perceived learning environment in physical education plays a pivotal role in influencing students' motivation and engagement. A positive learning environment, characterized by factors such as improvement, important role or autonomy support, teacher care which eliminates punishment and unequal recognition, and cooperative classmate interactions, fosters intrinsic motivation and promotes students' intentions for physical activity both within and beyond the classroom.

Influence of Perceived Learning Environment on Motivation of PE majors

Table 5 presents the influence of perceived learning environment variables on the motivation levels of physical education (PE) major students, as determined through regression analysis. The table displays unstandardized coefficients, standardized coefficients (Beta), and associated statistical values for each perceived learning environment indicator.

Table 5. *Influence of Perceived Learning Environment on Motivation of PE majors*

Variable	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	p
	B	SE	Beta (β)		
Effort/Improvement	.284	.087	.233	3.278	.001
Important Role	.151	.113	.097	1.338	.182
Cooperative Learning	.074	.040	.125	1.857	.065
Punishment for Mistakes	.004	.048	.007	.074	.941
Unequal Recognition	-.050	.053	-.105	-.933	.352
Intra-Class Rivalry	.125	.053	.241	2.356	.019

Note. Constant=1.751, $F(6,220)=6.124^{***}$, $p<.001$, $R^2=.147$

As seen in table 5, effort/improvement emerges as a significant predictor of motivation among PE major students, with a positive unstandardized coefficient of .284 ($p < .001$) and a standardized coefficient (β) of .233. This indicates that for every unit increase in perceived effort/improvement in the learning environment, there is a corresponding increase in motivation levels among students, holding other variables constant. Similarly, Intra-class rivalry demonstrates a significant positive influence on motivation, with an unstandardized coefficient of .125 ($p = .019$) and a standardized coefficient (β) of .241. This suggests that perceptions of intra-class rivalry within the learning environment contribute to higher levels of motivation among PE major students.

Also, depicted in table 5 are variables such as important role and cooperative learning which exhibit weaker and nonsignificant influences on motivation, as indicated by their unstandardized coefficients of .151 ($p = .182$) and .074 ($p = .065$) respectively. While the standardized coefficients suggest some influence, these effects are not statistically significant at the conventional threshold of $p < .05$. Punishment for mistakes and unequal recognition also fail to exert significant influences on motivation, with both variables demonstrating negligible unstandardized coefficients and nonsignificant p-values.

The findings of this study contribute significantly to the existing body of literature, highlighting on the various factors that influence motivation levels among physical education students. Willoughby's (2022) research identified perceptions of mastery climates, competence, and relatedness need support as significant predictors of motivation quantity and quality among students in physical education. Similarly, Ferrer-Caja and Weiss (2000) highlighted the importance of perceived competence and goal orientations as predictors of intrinsic motivation among students in this field. Additionally, Hines (2022) identified predictors of motivation among PE majors, including task-involved motivational climate, basic psychological need satisfaction, and self-determined motivation.

In this study, effort/improvement and intra-class rivalry emerged as the strongest predictors of motivation among physical education students, emphasizing the importance of fostering supportive learning environments and addressing intra-class dynamics to enhance student motivation. It becomes evident that multiple factors contribute to the motivation levels of physical education students, ranging from perceptions of competence and goal orientations to the quality of the learning environment and the motivational climate. By considering these multifaceted influences, educators and policymakers can develop targeted interventions and strategies aimed at promoting positive motivational experiences and optimizing learning outcomes for physical education students.

Conclusion

This study has illustrated the intricate relationship between the perceived learning environment and motivation among physical education (PE) major students. Through careful quantitative analysis, it became evident that students perceive their learning environment in PE classes at a notably high level, accompanied by high levels of motivation. Notably, factors such as effort/improvement and intra-class rivalry emerged as significant predictors of student motivation, emphasizing their important roles in shaping students' motivational experiences within the PE context. These findings contribute significantly to the existing body of literature, providing insights that can inform educational practices and policies aimed at optimizing learning experiences and outcomes for PE major students.

Moving forward, several recommendations can be proposed based on the study's findings. Firstly, educators should prioritize efforts to cultivate a supportive and inclusive learning environment within PE classes, emphasizing aspects such as effort, improvement, and positive peer dynamics. Additionally, providing opportunities for autonomy and competence can foster intrinsic motivation and promote students' sense of mastery and competence. Addressing intra-class dynamics, such as rivalry and unequal recognition, is also crucial in promoting positive social interactions and mitigating factors that may undermine student motivation. Furthermore, interventions and support services should be tailored to address the diverse needs and preferences of individual students, recognizing that motivation may vary among students and may be influenced by a multitude of factors. Finally, continuous evaluation and adjustment of interventions are essential to ensure their effectiveness and responsiveness to evolving student needs and contexts.

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